

Large Language Models for Data Extraction in Toxicology: Implications and Lessons Learned from the Clinical Evidence Domain

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Abstract

A living review of automated data extraction methods for clinical systematic reviews identified 76 papers up to the end of 2022 describing unique extraction algorithms and assessed their methods and quality of reporting. The current ~~in-progress~~ update for 2024 observed a rapid increase in papers ~~compared with 2022~~; it now includes 117 papers, of which 17 employ Large Language Models (LLMs) to automate data extraction from randomized controlled trials. In this commentary, we describe findings from the analysis of these LLM automation papers and discuss parallels to the field of automated data extraction in toxicology. We describe the evaluation strategies and reporting observed in LLM publications and focus on inconsistencies and potential pitfalls that may bias how the performance of LLMs is perceived by ~~those likely to apply them to support systematic reviews-researchers involved with systematic reviews~~. We then discuss potential applications of LLMs in evidence mapping and good practice in the reporting of LLM automation methods – based

on a checklist and guideline developed during the 2023 Evidence Synthesis hackathon in Newcastle (UK).

1. Introduction

As interest grows in integrating generative large language models (LLMs) into systematic review workflows, gaps in evaluation standards, reproducibility, and fair benchmarking have emerged. This commentary, grounded in a living systematic review (LSR) of automated data extraction, reveals a trend of declining adherence to established reporting best practices. Newer and larger models still show safety concerns, and some publications unexpectedly indicate that smaller models can outperform LLMs in certain areas. This applies especially in domains with high-quality gold-standard datasets where more rigorous and reproducible validation is achieved with non-generative AI architectures. In this commentary, we highlight key architectural differences among language models, implications for literature review automation, and present a practical evaluation and reporting template developed during the 2023 Evidence Synthesis Hackathon to improve rigor and transparency in this evolving field.

1.1 Living Review of Data Extraction Methods

The 17 LLM articles included in this commentary originate from a published living review of data extraction methods that includes a total of 117 articles (Schmidt et al., 2025). This commentary focuses on 17 recent LLM studies identified in a broader living systematic review (LSR) of 117 publications on data extraction methods (Schmidt et al., 2025). The LSR uses 2020 as the literature search start. Briefly, starting in 2020 and conducts regular searches of authors searched different sources but currently include PubMed, ACL Anthology, arXiv, OpenAlex via EPPI-Reviewer, and the dblp computer science bibliography database sources. The latest The current review updatesearch covers includes publications up to August 2024 and OpenAlex content up to September 2024 and captures original methods for automating data extraction of elements necessary to support systematic reviews. It includes articles publishing original data extraction automation approaches for study characteristics, such as the PICO (population, intervention, comparator, outcome) data. For Full inclusion criteria and methodological details can be found in the LSR publication in- and exclusion criteria and more detailed description of the methods, please see the LSR publication (Schmidt et al., 2025). Additional resources, including the Up-to-date information, as well as PRISMA2020 diagram and interactive maps are available on the LSR website.¹

¹ https://l-ena.github.io/living_review_data_extraction/LatestUpdates.html

1.2 Differences between generative LLMs and other neural networks

Both Large Language Models (LLMs) and smaller pretrained language models (PLMs) have the potential to play important roles in automating data extraction of information from both clinical and environmental toxicology literature (Schmidt et al., 2023; Schmitt et al., 2018). These two formats differ significantly in size, capabilities, resource requirements, and applications.

LLMs such as the Generative Pretrained Transformer (GPT) described in, (Radford et al. (2018)) are neural networks based on the transformer architecture ((Vaswani et al., 2017) and trained on massive corpora. These models are capable of capturing the highly complex statistical relationships and nuances needed to model human language. -smaller models such as BERT, which stands for Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers (Devlin et al., 2019; Vaswani et al., 2017)^[1] are computational models of human language used in the fields of natural language processing, understanding and synthesis. Generative LLMs are currently very large; in the case of GPT-4 estimates suggest that the model contains more than 1.5 trillion numeric parameters². (Vaswani et al., 2017)^[2] (Vaswani et al., 2017)^[3]. They are capable of capturing the highly complex statistical relationships and nuances needed to model human language. Generative LLMs are very large, in the case of GPT-4 there are estimates that the model contains more than 1.5 trillion³ parameters. They are trained with text from large data sources such as the internet or books and training requires extensive amounts of computational power. Training is typically focused on predicting missing text, based on some-number-of surrounding words (the context window). This ability to predict text allows LLMs to be used to readily generate new text based on user provided context, such as in answering a question. Larger context windows require the use of larger neural networks and are more computationally expensive; but provide increased accuracy as model predictions can be sensitive to both nearby context (e.g., in the same sentence) and remote context (e.g., in a prior section or paragraph). GPT-4o can use-consider approximately 96,000 words⁴ tokens^[4] of context, sufficient to incorporate the entire context of a research article and to answer questions about scientific articles.

² <https://the-decoder.com/gpt-4-has-a-trillion-parameters/> and <https://explodingtopics.com/blog/gpt-parameters> (last accessed 05th Nov 2024)

³ <https://the-decoder.com/gpt-4-has-a-trillion-parameters/> and <https://explodingtopics.com/blog/gpt-parameters> (last accessed 05th Nov 2024)

⁴ <https://platform.openai.com/docs/models/gpt-4o> (last accessed 19th Feb 2025)

~~t(Lai et al., 2025)~Specializedspecializedanswer questions about the article.~~

PLMs such as BERT (Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers) share the transformer foundation but are smaller and trained commonly fine-tuned for specific tasks. Their output is not generative – they classify existing text or represent it in vector-format for downstream processing (a process called embedding). Smaller Pre-trained Language Models (PLMs), such as BERT, are based on the same principles. These models are also trained on existing text, but they have fewer parameters and can be downloaded in full, adjusted, and deployed to make predictions on GPU or strong CPU home and office computers. These models generally have lower performance in applications such as question answering and are limited to extractive methods where the model’s answer is always an extract from the input context. However, PLMs they are often sufficiently capable for tasks such as the classifications of words, sentences, or documents (Devlin et al., 2019) and can be used to create inputs for other machine learning algorithms and statistical models. A direct comparison of PLMs and LLMs is shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Direct comparison of a PLM (BERT-base) with a LLM (GPT-4). Please note that LLM information is based on estimates from blogs and other online sources due to a lack of official information by its provider.

Topic	PLM: BERT	LLM: GPT-4 architecture
Architecture	Based on transformers (Devlin et al., 2019; Vaswani et al., 2017)	Same as PLMs
Size	BERT-base example: 110M parameters (Devlin et al., 2019), the updated ModernBERT-base model has 149M (Warner et al., 2024).	GPT-4 example: Estimated 1.5-1.8 trillion parameters ⁵ , ~15,450 x bigger than BERT-base
Pre-training	Own pre-training or continued pre-training is feasible due to small network size. Pre-training was originally	Leaks and estimates suggest usage of >10,000 A100 GPUs (40-80 GB memory each) for GPT-4 ⁷ producing costs in

⁵ <https://the-decoder.com/gpt-4-has-a-trillion-parameters/> and <https://explodingtopics.com/blog/gpt-parameters> (last accessed 05th Nov 2024)

⁷ https://colab.research.google.com/drive/1O99z9b115O66bT78r9ScslE_nOj5irN9 (last accessed 13/06/2025)

	completed in 4 days using 16 Google Cloud TPUs (Devlin et al., 2019), with an estimated cost between \$500-7000 ⁶	excess of \$50 million and taking >3 months.
Fine-tuning	Commonly fine-tuned locally using datasets such as EBM-NLP, adjusting all layers of the model. Single 8-16 GB desktop GPU or CPU is sufficient.	Fine-tuning layers of a cloud-deployed model, due to model size requirements ⁸ . The costs associated with this may be high, as noted by authors who fine-tuned GPT-3.5 but decided against doing so with GPT-4 (Lai et al., 2025).
Input	Text, the model will break sentences and words into tokens (Devlin et al., 2019)	Same as PLMs
Context length	BERT-base can process 512 tokens (~380 words) (Devlin et al., 2019), while ModernBERT extended context length to 8192 (~6000 words)	GPT-4o processes 128,000 tokens (~96,000 words)
Output	Encoder model: the model is discriminative, it outputs a vector with embeddings (numeric representation of input tokens). These embeddings can be used for classification of the tokens in the input text (Devlin et al., 2019).	Decoder model: the model is generative, it outputs new text. Users may also use the embeddings if needed. A comparison between PLM and LLM output is shown in Figure 1.

⁶ <https://syncedreview.com/2019/06/27/the-staggering-cost-of-training-sota-ai-models/> (last accessed 13/06/2025)

⁸ <https://platform.openai.com/docs/guides/fine-tuning> (last accessed 13/06/2025)

<p><u>Purpose</u></p>	<p><u>Specialized: the light-weight implementation is designed to enable task-specific fine-tuning. This process creates specialized model version for downstream prediction tasks.</u></p>	<p><u>General purpose: due to size and amount of information, these models are general purpose and are designed to be used with prompting instead of task-specific fine-tuning.</u></p>
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(Devlin et al., 2019)

1.3 Brief description of data extraction tasks

Named entity recognition (NER) is a foundational step in automating evidence extraction from clinical and toxicological literature, commonly focusing on instances of PICO (Population, Intervention, Control, Outcomes) classes (Schmidt et al., 2023); which is similar to PECO (Population, Exposure, Control, Outcomes) in toxicology research. Automated named-entity recognition (NER) is the process of extracting ~~pieces of~~ information (usually nouns or noun-phrases) from text. ‘Entities’ are instances of classes of concepts, for example ‘Berlin’ is an instance of the class ‘City’. ~~In the clinical research domain, NER commonly focuses on instances of PICO (Population, Intervention, Control, Outcomes) classes (Schmidt et al., 2023); which is similar to PECO (Population, Exposure, Control, Outcomes) in toxicology research.~~ In the past, the same PLM architectures based on transformers and long short-term memory networks have been used to automate extraction in both fields. Toxicology has datasets like those used in the TAC-SRIE challenge (Schmitt et al., 2018) which supports NER for animal studies while NLP (Natural Language Processing) in Evidence-based Medicine (EBM) has EBM-NLP (Nye et al., 2018). These datasets contain texts ~~offrom~~ published research, manually labelled with ~~entities~~entities, and can be used to train and evaluate language models for data extraction.

~~To be useful in practice, data can be extracted or highlighted to support semi-automated workflows; As shown in the papers listed in Table 2, data extraction involves additional tasks beyond NER, such as the extraction of relationships between entities, extraction of qualifiers on relationships, extraction of references, normalization of concepts to standardized terminologies, and resolving pronouns. As both NER and these additional data extraction tasks are not producing perfect results, in practice, data can be extracted or highlighted to support semi-automated~~

[workflows](#), implemented for example in RobotReviewer (Marshall et al., 2017) or Dextr (Walker et al., 2022). For more autonomous automation, these entities need to be resolved, evidence relations and effect directions need to be inferred and optionally normalized, as shown in the papers listed in Table 24.

Currently, so-called 'Error propagation cascading' is a barrier for the successful application of [data extraction](#) methods beyond NER in practice, but new approaches such as LLMs offer an opportunity to overcome this issue, as they can reduce the need for applying multiple task-specific models. The cascading happens. Methods suffer from the propagation of errors when multiple models (one for each task, applied successively) show incorporate errors across tasks resulting in increased magnitudes of errors due to propagating carrying forward mistakes made by the preceding models. (Cheng et al., 2025). New approaches such as LLMs offer an opportunity to overcome this issue, as they can reduce the need for applying multiple task-specific models.

Evaluation metrics and benchmark datasets

Critical evaluation and documentation of the performance of automated extraction methods is essential to ensure they are reliable and usable in practice. The F1 score is a quantitative validation metric that is the harmonic mean between positive predictive value (precision) and sensitivity (recall); F1 is often used in classification scenarios where the more important positive class is underrepresented. It is one of the most commonly used metrics for the validation of automated data extraction because it helps to distinguish low-quality high-recall algorithms that over-classify datapoints as 'positive' to obtain high recall from those algorithms that are able to also attain high precision (ie. minimise minimize false-positive predictions to reduce irrelevant data presented to downstream users of the automation system)

Domain specific LLMs like BioGPT have demonstrated promising results on biomedical extraction tasks outperforming earlier models like BioBERT. These results highlight the potential of LLMs to support evidence synthesis, though challenges remain with cost, transparency, and critical evaluation. BioGPT is an early example of a domain-specific generative language model pre-trained on large-scale biomedical literature based on the GPT-2 architecture. Although comprehensive head-to-head comparisons of humans vs. LLM for data extraction from scientific papers are currently lacking, domain-specific models such as BioGPT have shown potential. For example it achieved F1 scores of 38.42% and 44.98 % on KD-DTI and BC5CDR (BioCreative-5 Chemical-Disease Relation) end-to-end relation extraction tasks, respectively, and a 78.2%

accuracy on PubMedQA ([PubMed Question Answering](#)), setting new records in the field (Luo et al., 2022). For comparison, KD-DTI F1 scores using BioBERT were 14% lower. More recently, scores on BC5CDR- improved to >70% when fine-tuning GPT-3.5. There may be scope for improvement with more recent LLM architectures, but the authors noted that no experiments were carried out on GPT-4 architectures due to the cost associated with fine-tuning them (Lai et al., 2025). These results ~~suggest the~~[show-demonstrate](#) successful deployments of LLMs ~~to's~~ potential to ~~understand~~, summarise, and extract complex relationships from biomedical texts ~~that may surpass human capabilities~~ and indicates ~~its~~[their](#) potential to assist human experts in annotating and synthesizing information from scientific literature (Z. P. Wang et al., 2024). ~~However, F1 scores on these complex relation extraction datasets are low, and to put them into context, comprehensive head-to-head comparisons of humans vs. PLMs vs. LLMs are needed. Ideally the comparison would include not just precision or error rates for manual methods relative to these models, but also detailed exploration of the type of errors characteristic of each approach.~~

Table 2: Different steps in the automated data extraction process

Task	Example	Evaluation	Challenges	Representative publications
Named-entity recognition: to label all relevant data points in text	Detect every single word that describes a study population in an abstract.	Precision, recall, F1. Evaluation operates on the entity or token-level.	Class imbalance, there are more negative than positive words, which means that scores like specificity or accuracy are misleading.	Nye et al. (2018), Schmitt et al. (2018)
Entity resolution: to resolve and disambiguate all mentions of the same entity and group them	Single grouped or summarized version of a concept, e.g. 'placebo - controlled' and 'control group' → 'placebo' in an abstract.	For most entities this is a document-level task and an evaluation in terms of accuracy is adequate	Ambiguity and the need to infer information, missing information, error cascading	(Schmidt et al., 2024), Tim Reason et al. (2024)
Evidence inference: to extract relation	Create structured outputs of concept	Precision, recall, F1 of correctly identifying 'ICO'	Error cascading, high risk of creating factual	Wadhwa, DeYoung, et al. (2023), DeYoung et al. (2020), (Luo et al., 2022) (Walker et al., 2022)

s and directions of effect between concepts	relations , e.g. 'Intervention (Energy drink) leads to significantly higher Outcome (blood pressure) compared with Control (fruit juice). '	or 'ECO' triplets.	sounding but wrong output due to classification errors.	
Entity normalization: to link detected entities to concepts in structured vocabularies	MeSH (Medical Subject Headings) term normalization, e.g. 'blood pressure → hypertension, D006973',	Precision, recall, F1 and 'relaxed' methods where correct identification of related concepts is allowed	Error cascading, affected by sparsity because the label-space can be extremely large with little training data, ambiguity	Marshall et al. (2020) , Singh et al. (2017) (Walker et al.,2022)

Table 1: Different steps in the automated data extraction process

2. Application and validation of LLMs for data extraction

Are LLMs better than PLMs for data extraction?

The problem with the LLM vs. PLM comparison for data extraction lies in the fundamentally different objectives fulfilled by the two architectures⁹. It is an evaluation of discriminative task-specific PLMs that aim to classify existing text vs. generative general-purpose LLMs that produce new text outputs. The 17 LLM papers included in the aforementioned [living systematic review \(LSR\)](#) of data extraction update (see [Appendix_Maps_A](#)) showed that model performance is highly dependent on the perspective from which the evaluation is conducted (Schmidt et al., 2025). Figure 1 provides an example to visualise this problem.

⁹ <https://www.langtec.de/2024/06/11/evaluating-the-performance-of-large-language-models-for-information-extraction-a-comparative-study/?lang=en> (Last accessed 12/12/2024)

Predictors of postdischarge outcomes from information acquired shortly after admission for acute heart failure: a report from the Placebo-Controlled Randomized Study of the Selective A1 Adenosine Receptor Antagonist Rolofylline for Patients Hospitalized With Acute Decompensated Heart Failure and Volume Overload to Assess Treatment Effect on Congestion and Renal Function (PROTECT) Study.

BACKGROUND Acute heart failure is a common reason for admission, and outcome is often poor. Improved prognostic risk stratification may assist in the design of future trials and in patient management. Using data from a large randomized trial, we explored the prognostic value of clinical variables, measured at hospital admission for acute heart failure, to determine whether a few selected variables were inferior to an extended data set.

METHODS AND RESULTS The prognostic model included 37 clinical characteristics collected at baseline in PROTECT, a study comparing rolofylline and placebo in 2033 patients admitted with acute heart failure. Prespecified outcomes at 30 days were death or rehospitalization for any reason ; death or rehospitalization for cardiovascular or renal reasons ; and, at both 30 and 180 days, all-cause mortality. No variable had a c-index > 0.70, and few had values > 0.60 ; c-indices were lower for composite outcomes than for mortality. Blood urea was generally the strongest single predictor. Eighteen variables contributed independent prognostic information, but a reduced model using only 8 items (age, previous heart failure hospitalization, peripheral edema, systolic blood pressure, serum sodium, urea, creatinine, and albumin) performed similarly. For prediction of all-cause mortality at 180 days, the model c-index using all variables was 0.72 and for the simplified model, also 0.72. **CONCLUSIONS** A few simple clinical variables measured on admission in patients with acute heart failure predict a variety of adverse outcomes with accuracy similar to more complex models. However, predictive models were of only moderate accuracy, especially for outcomes that included nonfatal events. Better methods of risk stratification are required. **CLINICAL TRIAL REGISTRATION URL:** <http://www.clinicaltrials.gov>. Unique identifiers: NCT00328692 and NCT00354458

	EBM-NLP Gold Standard (discriminative, exhaustive)	LLM prediction (generative, summarising)
P	'acute heart failure ;', 'Patients Hospitalized With Acute Decompensated Heart Failure and Volume Overload', 'Acute heart failure', '2033 patients admitted with acute heart failure .', 'patients with acute heart failure	2033 patients admitted with acute heart failure
IC	'Placebo-Controlled', 'Selective A1 Adenosine Receptor Antagonist Rolofylline', 'rolofylline and placebo'	comparing rolofylline and placebo
O	['death or rehospitalization for any reason ; death or rehospitalization for cardiovascular or renal reasons ;', 'Blood urea', 'all-cause mortality', 'variety of adverse outcomes', 'accuracy', 'moderate accuracy', 'outcomes that included nonfatal events .']	Prespecified outcomes at 30 days were death or rehospitalization for any reason; death or rehospitalization for cardiovascular or renal reasons; and, at both 30 and 180 days, all-cause mortality

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P	'acute heart failure :', 'Patients Hospitalized With Acute Decompensated Heart Failure and Volume Overload', 'Acute heart failure', '2033 patients admitted with acute heart failure .', 'patients with acute heart failure	2033 patients admitted with acute heart failure
I C	'Placebo-Controlled', 'Selective A1 Adenosine Receptor Antagonist Rolofylline', 'rolofylline and placebo'	comparing rolofylline and placebo
O	['death or rehospitalization for any reason ; death or rehospitalization for cardiovascular or renal reasons ;', 'Blood urea', 'all-cause mortality', 'variety of adverse outcomes', 'accuracy', 'moderate accuracy', 'outcomes that included nonfatal events .']	Prespecified outcomes at 30 days were death or rehospitalization for any reason; death or rehospitalization for cardiovascular or renal reasons; and, at both 30 and 180 days, all-cause mortality

Figure 1: Discriminative versus generative data extraction on the abstract of Cleland et al. (2014) within EBM-NLP, for automatically extracting P (Population), IC (Intervention, Control) and O (Outcomes) entities in abstracts of randomized clinical trials with human participants.

2.1 Direct comparisons between LLMs and PLMs

PLMs consistently outperform LLMs on structured data extractions due to their token-level classification abilities. In head-to-head comparisons on public benchmark datasets such as Biomedical Language Understanding & Reasoning Benchmark (BLURB), which stands for Biomedical Language Understanding & Reasoning Benchmark (Gu et al., 2020) that focus on more straightforward data extraction and classification tasks in the biomedical domain, PLMs outperformed LLMs by significant margins (Gu et al., 2020). For BLURB, 11 tasks are evaluated using F1 scores, and two tasks were evaluated using accuracy. The, and the LLM obtained a

macro-averaged score of 58.5, which was 25% lower than the previous (Chen et al., 2023)^[66]. It was also shown on EBM-NLP, CONSORT-TM ([CONsolidated Standards Of Reporting Trials – Text Mining](#)) and other smaller datasets that PLMs demonstrated superior performance especially when sufficient training data is available (Cao et al., 2024; Ghosh et al., 2024; Jiang et al., 2024)^[66]. One reason contributing to this performance gap is that traditionally these tasks have the objective of creating structured data based on unstructured text inputs and evaluation operates on a verbatim basis where the correct answer is always a subset of the existing text (see Figure 1). The evaluation of PLMs is based on correctly labelling words as entities, and poor evaluation scores such as recall (sensitivity) may be obtained if the model correctly identifies one instance of an entity but misses it in the next sentence. Generative LLMs do not operate this way; they provide a summary of all entities across a document which explains their poorer performance scores on NER benchmarks.

2.2 Application of LLMs to complex tasks

The application of PLMs to entity resolution is less well studied (ie. resolving multiple mentions of the same entity within the reference text; such as abbreviations, indirect references, and synonyms). With PLMs, entity resolution would [potentially](#) require multiple models (one for NER and an additional one for resolving and summarising entities) which [increases their complexity](#) is [complex](#). PLMs typically require multiple models for tasks like entity resolution, which can introduce complexity and errors being carried forward across models (Caselli et al., 2015) <https://www.langtec.de/2024/06/11/evaluating-the-performance-of-large-language-models-for-information-extraction-a-comparative-study/?lang=en>. LLMs, on the other hand, can perform such tasks in a more integrated manner. ~~LLMs appear to naturally skip the step of NER (i.e., exhaustive extraction of concepts) and directly provide resolved entities by omitting the explicit NER step of exhaustive concept extraction and directly generate resolved entities.~~ Rather than creating structured output, they provide further unstructured summary of entities. [This integrated approach reduces the need for chained models and can streamline downstream tasks.](#)

2.3 Fair and reproducible evaluation of LLMs for data extraction

~~The following section describes evaluation methods in current LLMs publications, including trends and methodological shortfalls. It also highlights differences between discriminative (PLM) and generative outputs (LLM) that may lead to biased evaluation results in head-to-head comparisons. Recent LLM studies commonly evaluate performance using overall accuracy metrics, particularly in zero shot prompting scenarios. Such evaluations, especially when using~~

[prompts only, are highly sensitive to prompt quality, dataset splits, subject, and domain specific variations.](#)

[In the LLM papers included in the LSR, Pperformance is often evaluated in terms of overall accuracy \(i.e., correctness of the output\) and, especially in zero-shot prompting scenarios. When using prompts alone, results are, is highly dependent on prompt quality, dataset splits, and subject.](#) Performance can also vary significantly depending on the domain and study design. One small study by Gartlehner et al. (2024) involved 10 RCTs from one systematic review and reported reaching 95% accuracy on data from seven (having used three for prompt development). Another small study assessing data extraction from animal studies, social science, and human clinical publications from PubMed found that average accuracies were much lower, ranging between 72% to 82%, having used two for prompt development and 10 for evaluation in each domain (Schmidt et al., 2024). These numbers illustrate the wide range of evaluation results between small studies with limited datasets, and the importance of maintaining strictly separate subsets of data for prompt development and evaluation.

The separate evaluation dataset is important to avoid overestimating the LLM's performance and contaminating results. Overestimation can happen if [researchers authors](#) overfit prompts to perform well on a small selection of manually labelled data and then blindly apply them to the rest of the dataset. The remaining texts may have different characteristics – thus resulting in undetected poor performance with potential implications for the validity of the resulting literature review results. The only way of minimizing the risk of overfitting is to evaluate LLM predictions on manually labelled, [randomly selected and held-out evaluation data. As part of the 2023 Evidence Synthesis Hackathon, one team developed RefRandomiser – a web-based tool that randomises and splits data into batches for LLM and other AI evaluations, resulting in data that would be very useful for the transparency of model evaluation](#)¹⁰.

[Moreover, comparing PLMs and LLMs directly is inherently problematic. PLMs are discriminative and often require multi-component architectures for complex tasks, whereas LLMs generate free-form outputs. Evaluating both using the same metrics can introduce bias, as LLMs may be penalized for stylistic variability rather than actual errors \(see Figure 1\). Comparisons between the two architectures are therefore complicated. LLMs are generative models and thus their](#)

¹⁰ <https://refrandomiser.streamlit.app/>

~~performance is not adequate when forcibly assessed in a way that suits discriminative models.~~

Similarly, PLMs are not generative and thus require more complex architectures to approximate LLM functionality on summarisation tasks; which means that they currently do not attain levels of accuracy demonstrated by LLMs. [Finally, it's critical to consider the impact of the models on the overall systematic review workflow as workflows may be altered to reflect the strengths of the models, further impacting considerations such as the time to conduct a review and human assessment of model results.](#)

3. Challenges and risks associated with LLMs

3.1 Shifting workload and creating unsustainable evaluation scenarios

Evaluation of PLMs and LLMs highlight a key trade-off: PLMs require upfront investment in dataset creation, whereas LLMs reduce that initial burden but shift the human workload to evaluation. Both approaches involve sustainability and testing considerations —albeit at different stages in the model lifecycle. Understanding where and how this human effort is needed is essential for developing scalable and reusable data extraction methods. This creates potential sustainability challenges especially in validating outputs overtime. ‘A stitch in time saves nine’ is an old English proverb serving to warn of the risks of delaying tasks. One stitch applied when the hole is small will save a lengthier repair when the hole is larger. Similarly, PLM-based models require time and resource investment early on, to create gold-standard datasets for training and evaluation but once the dataset is available, no more manual work is required for evaluation. Nye et al. (2018), for example, hired crowd workers to create the EBM-NLP dataset. Once created the dataset was subsequently used in 28 other publications, thereby reducing downstream human effort., the dataset was used by them and at least 28 other publications(Schmidt et al., 2025) ~~(Schmidt et al., 2023)~~. Ideally each reuse would include an evaluation of performance or some degree of validation. One drawback is that gold-standard datasets are typically optimized for narrowly defined tasks and specific source corpora, limiting their generalizability. While shared benchmark datasets are valuable for structured domains such as randomized controlled trials (RCTs), their relevance may diminish in less standardized contexts like environmental data extraction, where annotation practices often vary and may not align with specific application needs.

Evaluating LLMs on binary classification tasks is straightforward, as existing labelled corpora can be re-used. This includes for example the automation of screening decisions or tagging records with pre-defined tags. With prompt-based LLM data extraction the situation is more complex because LLMs are designed to summarize and create new outputs, rather than classifying existing texts (see Figure 1). LLMs may save initial workload by not requiring gold-standard data up-front, but due to their generative nature they require multiple iterations of manual checking and validation, ideally and then repeated checking and validation when the upstream model is updated.

Additionally, access to and oversight of LLM training data are often limited, making the issue of data contamination a potential concern. For instance, while open datasets such as those from CLEF¹¹ may be appropriate for training purpose-built pre-trained language models (PLMs), their use in evaluating general-purpose LLMs is problematic, as the same content—such as systematic reviews—may have been included in the LLMs' training corpus. As a result, such evaluations risk over-estimating genuine task performance through memorization of content, undermining the validity of the assessment.

Datasets for PLMs and machine-learning

Publicly available, reusable datasets make PLM evaluation sustainable. During the ongoing and yet unpublished latest LSR update we discovered ~~at least~~ 76 datasets for data extraction of clinical evidence, of which 33 are deposited in repositories available to the public ~~(Schmidt et al., 2023)~~¹². The clearly defined classes and labels in these datasets enable re-training and re-evaluation of ~~(discriminative)~~ model predictions over and over, without further manual intervention. ~~(Schmidt et al., 2025)~~. ~~This represents a sustainable scenario - provided that researchers publish datasets and code in an accessible and well-documented manner. This presents a rather sustainable situation— if researchers publish datasets and code in an accessible manner, as is the current trend, then in that case,~~ the training and evaluation of extraction methods can be done in a time-efficient and sustainable way because ~~plenty of~~ training and evaluation datasets ~~with varying scope, annotation strategies, and content~~ are available. ~~However~~ Additionally, this diversity of datasets with no overlapping data is crucial in order to ensure that the data extraction research community does not overfit their methods to produce good results on only one specific (and possibly outdated) dataset.

~~Gold-standard datasets in toxicology, while valuable within their intended scope, often have limited applicability beyond the specific research questions, corpora, or annotation strategies they were developed for. Experiences such as the NIST TAC preparation (Schmitt et al., 2018) highlight methodological complexities involved in dataset creation, where choices made for one context may not generalize well to others. This underscores the importance of transparent documentation to enable researchers to assess the relevance of a dataset for their specific needs. To address issues of alignment, overfitting, and limited generalizability, there is a growing need for broadly~~

¹¹ https://clefehealth.imag.fr/clefehealth.imag.fr/index49be.html?page_id=215 (last accessed 18/07/2025)

¹² Citation of previously published version of the LSR does not contain the updated number of references and datasets mentioned in this paragraph.

annotated, domain-specific datasets and a community-driven infrastructure to share datasets, document their strengths and limitations, and collectively identify gaps in coverage. One such platform could be Huggingface¹³.

Challenges related to the validation of LLMs for data extraction

LLMs are considered as transformative and disruptive technology widely regarded as revolutionary because they can achieve high performance without training on additional gold standard data sets – which is a substantial departure from previous methods (e.g., NLP, ML). Instead, a user can prompt a model to perform a task without additional examples (or providing a very limited set of examples), a concept called zero or k-shot prompting. This removes the barrier of constructing training data that previously prevented automation methods being used in practice. This eliminates the need to construct extensive training datasets, which previously limited the practical use of automation methods in both clinical and toxicology research.

However, LLMs require human-supervision when developing prompts for specific data extraction targets and it is often only feasible to use small development datasets because humans need to constantly re-assess and tailor prompts during development. More crucially, LLMs often require humans to manually evaluate their generative predictions. More importantly, LLMs typically require human evaluation of their generative outputs on separate evaluation datasets. This process may need to be repeated multiple times because LLM output (and its accuracy) has shown small changes between runs that may not be controllable via its parameters (T. Reason et al., 2024; Schmidt et al., 2024). In contrast, when automating screening decisions with LLMs or tagging articles, it is possible to automatically generate prompts based on inclusion criteria from underlying reviews and to automate the evaluation process.

When forcing LLM output to fit pre-labelled datasets for data extraction, such as EBM-NLP, then their performance may decline and appear lower than it is in reality, as discussed in the previous section. This means that while no human input is needed for LLM training, human workload is shifted to the concentrated in the evaluation phase. Similarly to Nye et al. with the creation of their re-usable dataset, others hired workers to evaluate their LLM predictions (Wadhwa, Amir, et al., 2023; Wadhwa, DeYoung, et al., 2023) – with the difference that their LLM prediction evaluation was only applicable to their specific projects, their LLM versions, and their extraction strategies.

¹³ <https://huggingface.co/datasets> (last accessed 18/07/2025)

Other LLM publications that used smaller, sometimes selective convenience datasets and zero- or few-shot prompting were similarly forced to invest manual work to evaluate LLM outputs, suggesting that the need for some form of ‘gold standard’ still exists in the LLM space. These evaluations may become less valid over time as LLMs get updated and re-released, and similarly to conventional machine-learning they are not guaranteed to be representative of how the model would perform on a different dataset or with a different literature review topic.

Schmidt et al. (2024) discuss these issues around resource-intensive manual LLM evaluation and the lack of meaningful validation metrics that can be applied automatically. BLEU (bilingual evaluation understudy) and ROUGE (Recall-Oriented Understudy for Gisting Evaluation) scores are existing automated validation scores that were developed for the related fields of summarisation and machine-translation, using heuristics such as n-gram overlaps between predicted and reference text (Lin, 2004; Papineni et al., 2002). When testing BLEU and ROUGE for automatically scoring LLM predictions across 100 references from EBM-NLP, Schmidt et al. (2024) found that the resulting scores were a poor representation of the actual LLM performance. ~~because the~~ Although many LLM predictions were accurate, they frequently exhibited low textual overlap with the reference standard. LLM’s generative predictions, despite being correct, were often too dissimilar to the reference standard.

Joseph et al. (2024) discuss the same issue – they provide a dataset with PICO-structured summaries from three LLMs together with human-annotated evaluations of the LLM output. They tested evaluation methods employing heuristics such as counting common chunks of texts or words between summaries and the true answer to score LLMs. By sharing it they challenge other researchers to develop automated ways of assessing the LLM output in a manner that is meaningful and concordant with human assessment (Joseph et al., 2024). Having these automated evaluation measures means having a viable alternative to fully manual evaluations, which is an important step towards the creation of new and trustworthy data extraction methods that can be validated at scale.

3.2 Risks and practical challenges

~~General issues and caveats~~ Misclassifications and hallucinations

Poor handling of complex, missing, implied, or ambiguous information are caveats frequently described with PLMs, and there are important issues because they lead to misclassifications. These issues apply to toxicology studies as well as to clinical research because the complexity,

language, and format of research texts is comparable. PLM misclassifications express themselves in two ways: As false-negatives where a piece of information is overlooked and never extracted, or as false-positive, where a wrong (but existing) word within the text is falsely labelled as relevant.

LLMs were equally shown to produce incorrect outputs, with the exception that the language describing errors is more human-like, using terms such as ‘hallucination’ or ‘confusion’.

Hallucination is an issue where generative models generate plausible sounding text, aiming to satisfy the user rather than being factually correct. In the included papers, hallucinations that appear specifically often when extracting or interpreting data related to results of trials such as numerical values or relations (Joseph et al., 2024; T. Reason et al., 2024; Z. Wang et al., 2024; Yun et al., 2024). Kartchner et al. (2023) described hallucinations that manifested themselves as the LLM adding and then answering its own data extraction questions. Possible strategies for preventing hallucinations are explicitly prompting LLMs to only consider provided context and to extract terms such as ‘Unclear’ or ‘Not Available’ if information cannot be found. However, this may not always be reliable and models can still produce random hallucinations. At the same time, providers of LLMs are working on minimising hallucinations, with benchmarks such as the ‘FACTS Grounding’ dataset and leaderboard by Google¹⁴, aimed at quantifying how factually correct leading LLMs are. Currently as of 17th July 2025, Google’s Gemini-2.5-Pro leads, with Anthropic’s Claude-3-5-Sonnet 4th, Deepseek-R1 6th, and O1 as OpenAI’s best-placed model in 14th place. This benchmark aims to show how well LLMs ground their response in facts from a provided context, and responses are judged by a group of LLMs. FactPICO is a benchmark with similar aims, focused on contexts from RCTs (Joseph et al., 2024). A review of LLM architectures described up-front costs, data protection and security, lack of explainability, and potentially biased training processes, data, and confirmation bias in users as other major concerns (Wornow et al., 2023).

Practical considerations

Cost and environmental impact particularly apply to researchers and tool developers who plan to process very large datasets (eg. the entirety of PubMed) with an LLM (Ren et al., 2024). Researchers should consider the environmental impact and sustainability of applying LLMs to large datasets and may first apply smaller, high-recall PLMs to filter potentially irrelevant records. This may change over the coming years, as LLM providers continue to refine training processes and model architectures to create smaller and more efficient models (Yang et al., 2024).

¹⁴ <https://www.kaggle.com/benchmarks/google/facts-grounding> (last accessed 17/07/2025)

When using automation tools with LLM integration, users should always check if the tool providers share clear, numeric, and absolute validation metrics for their approaches. Statements from start-up tool developers claiming relative improvements should be handled with care. This includes sales tactics such as claiming for example “Over 40% improved accuracy of the ‘Pro-Version’ as compared to the free-tier” without providing baseline numbers or a reference to a benchmark dataset.

This commentary focuses on the technological and data-scientific aspects of LLM use. Readers with deeper interest in practical implications of AI in evidence synthesis may refer to the draft of the RAISE guidance. The “*Responsible AI in Evidence Synthesis (RAISE): guidance and recommendations*” ~~are~~ is a collaboration between the Cochrane, Campbell, JBI, the International Collaboration for Automation in Systematic Reviews (ICASR), and others. While currently under development, an early draft provides recommendations for individuals and ~~organisations~~ organizations with key roles in the ‘Evidence-synthesis ecosystem’ such as evidence synthesists, methodologists, tool developers, ~~organisations~~ organizations producing evidence, publishers, and funders (!!! INVALID CITATION !!! (Thomas et al., 2025)).

4. Potential LLM applications in evidence-mapping

Large evidence and gap maps are useful tools in the field of environmental health and toxicology to categorize and ~~visuatise~~ visualize research trends and knowledge gaps (Wolffe et al., 2020). ~~There has been growing use of thhte evidenc-e map format in public health since. Walker et al. (2018), for example, -demonstrated the approach in a review that mapped published health effects evidence of transgenerational inheritance.~~ They involve broad searches and a diverse evidence-base, especially in cases where whole groups of chemicals are mapped at the same time, such as the PFAS-Tox project mapping references on 29 ~~perfluoroalkyl and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS)~~ chemicals (Pelch et al., 2022). These maps are relevant to policy-making or to inform downstream systematic review planning (Wolffe et al., 2020; Wolffe et al., 2019). ~~In the following we will present examples for non-LLM methods as well as recent LLM evidence-mapping and tagging research carried out with the Dextr and EPPI-Reviewer tools.~~

4.1 Non-LLM automation

Prior to LLMs, large-scale evidence mapping relied on manual and machine-assisted approaches such as priority screening and early stopping. Due to their larger scope, searches for evidence and gap maps may produce large amounts of results, leading to high workloads in screening and categorizing references (Campbell et al., 2025).

Several such large evidence maps were published in recent years, using manual (Pelch et al., 2022), and¹⁵, register-based (Olker et al., 2022), and¹⁶, or machine-assisted workflows which includes filtering, priority-screening or early-stopping of screening (Keshava et al., 2020; Shirke Avanti et al., 2024; Taylor et al., 2023).

4.2 LLM-based automation of screening and tagging

LLM usage to support evidence mapping may—as expected—not produce 100% correct categorization of evidence but nevertheless has potential to accelerate the processing of thousands of articles. As anticipated, employing an LLM for evidence mapping may not achieve perfect categorisation/categorization accuracy; however, it has potential to accelerate the processing of large volumes of literature.

A recent unpublished feasibility study at the EPPI-Centre by the Campbell Collaboration and the American Institutes of Research demonstrated the potential of GPT-4 to fully automate screening and categorization in evidence mapping. for such an LLM-supported evidence map outside the toxicology domain was conducted by researchers at the EPPI-Centre and supported by the Campbell Collaboration and the American Institutes for Research. They mapped evidence concerning equity research and artificial intelligence, using GPT-4 within EPPI-Reviewer to fully automate screening and categorization of records. Human-validated sensitivity for screening was perfect at 100% with 93% specificity. Human validation indicated 100 % sensitivity and 93 % specificity for the screening task, while accuracy of map categorizations assessed based on 157 titles and abstracts was 90%; with 7% categorized as minor and only 3% major errors¹⁷. This

¹⁵ <https://www.atsdr.cdc.gov/ToxProfiles/SEM-for-Methylene-chloride.pdf>

¹⁶

https://epi.figshare.com/articles/presentation/Evidence_Map_for_Ecological_Toxicity_of_Cyanotoxins_using_ECOTOXicology_Knowledgebase_Systematic_Protocols/24294973?file=42640621

¹⁷ <https://eppi.ioe.ac.uk/epi-vis/Review/Index/536>

indicates a substantial potential for LLMs to be deployed to automatically map research in a robust manner.

~~In the context of environmental health science literature assessments, the integration of LLM prompts within Dextr – a web-based data extraction tool – is currently being explored. Dextr processes full-text PDFs to support data extraction for systematic reviews and systematic evidence maps. While format analyses are currently being developed,~~ [In environmental health applications, Dextr, a web-based data extraction tool, integrates LLMs to process full-text PDFs for systematic review and evidence mapping.](#) preliminary, unpublished [impressions data](#) suggest [LLM performance that LLMs in Dextr perform](#) at least as well as, and potentially better than, the NLP models that have been rigorously validated and published (Walker et al., 2022). LLMs demonstrate a strong capability to accurately identify and extract key concepts relevant to environmental health science assessments, such as exposures, endpoints, exposure assessment methods, population, and race/ethnicity.

The use of carefully designed LLM prompts plays an essential role in tailoring the extraction process to focus on specific concepts, enabling targeted information retrieval. For example, in systematic evidence mapping, a LLM prompt engineered to identify only neurological endpoints within a large body of literature related to a broad exposure can quickly highlight the endpoints most relevant to the objectives without identifying all evaluated endpoints. Additionally, LLMs in Dextr have been used to accurately categorize exposures into pre-determined categories for systematic evidence maps. The prompts offer flexibility by allowing dynamic refinement of extraction criteria, ensuring that subtle or context-specific entities are identified and categorized appropriately. This categorization helps standardize data extraction and enables seamless visualization in evidence maps, which are essential for identifying research gaps and synthesizing findings in an accessible format. Leveraging the adaptability of LLM prompts allows for expansion beyond standard NER workflows, creating extraction schemas that meet the specific needs of environmental health science research. These initial observations highlight the potential of LLMs to improve efficiency, scalability, and precision in data extraction workflows, offering promising opportunities for innovation in systematic evidence synthesis and wider policy- or decision-making processes.

~~However, it remains crucial to clearly define methods and to report them in a transparent and accessible manner.~~ [Transparent reporting of LLM supported methods is essential.](#) Interactive

maps with ~~categorization~~[categorization of](#) results can be deployed online, while methods may be reported via registered protocols, pre-prints, self-publication, or academic journals.

~~To support researchers who plan to conduct LLM-related automation research in the reporting of their methods,~~ a group at the 2023 Newcastle Evidence Synthesis Hackathon created an evaluation and reporting template that may be used by researchers employing LLMs for screening, data extraction, or other automation research [that will be described in the following section](#).

5. LLM evaluation template

~~We developed the~~[This template was developed for researchers with a background in evidence synthesis who wish to develop LLM-based methods guided by best-practice standards in data science \(Schmidt et al., 2024\). Within the LLM papers in the LSR we observed a tendency of incomplete reporting about random dataset splitting, model choice, prompt development, and description of appropriate validation metrics \(when compared to previous standard of reporting seen with PLMs and ML\). The evaluation template can be used for planning and reporting of methods, to increase the standard of reporting and facilitate analysis and re-use of methods.](#)

The ~~evaluation~~ template shown in Figure 2 covers nine key pieces of information for researchers to include in manuscripts describing LLM automation methods. In the original paper, we conducted a feasibility study on LLM data extraction on clinical, social science, and animal studies as well as an analysis of LLM stability and describe the template in more depth (Schmidt et al., 2024). However, the template is also applicable in the toxicology and environmental review automation domain, and Figure 2 shows an adapted (fictional) example of an LLM-automated evidence map and suggestions how template sections could be filled.

1. **Research question/s:** Specify the question/s you are trying to answer with your evaluation.
(RQ1) How does the extraction of data items for a toxicology evidence map compare between a LLM and humans? (RQ2) How stable are the results across multiple runs?
2. **Model parameter/algorithm:** Name the model you are planning to evaluate.
LLM – GPT-4 with prompts submitted via OpenAI API. The model used will be '2024-06-01-preview, accessed on 30-31 October 2024.
3. **Comparator/s:** Name the algorithm/s or form/s of 'gold standard' that you are comparing to. Make clear whether they are an alternative model/algorithm or human generated data.
Categorizations on title/abstract level - new 'gold standard' human-agreed data.
4. **Performance measures:** Name the variable/s to be measured that are anticipated to be dependent on the model/algorithm.
(RQ1) Precision, recall, F1. Binary assessment if LLM adhered to the prescribed categorizations. (RQ2) Human assessment whether multiple runs of the same prompt yielded equal, small, or significant changes.
5. **Variables of interest:** State variables or conditions that might be related to the performance of the model/algorithm or the generalisability of the findings.
Type of map categorizations that could differ in performance and generalizability, eg. populations, exposures, type of procedure (in vitro vs. In vivo) might differ in level of difficulty.
6. **Dataset:** Specify how the data will be acquired. Name the dataset if using a pre-existing source. Explain any new data that needs to be generated to answer the research question/s.
Dataset: Novel dataset including 100 titles/abstracts with labelled categorizations, split into 10 for prompt development and 190 for testing.
7. **Sub-task/s:** Note any distinct (possibly standalone) tasks that are required for enabling the evaluation, and whether the sub-tasks require their own self-contained evaluation.
Prompt development informed by data in the development dataset, with the aim to generate viable prompts that will be submitted to GPT-4
8. **Repeated trials/simulation runs:** State how many times will the experiment be performed. This can be used to assess stability of performance.
LLM predictions on the test set three times to check for inconsistencies in output.
9. **Analysis:** State how data will be analysed.
(RQ1) Precision, recall, F1 for each evidence category separately, the LLM will be prompted to return data in a structured format, humans will be required to judge if LLM adhered to categories and provide error percentages. (RQ2) human qualitative assessment of stability in terms of descriptive statistics (percentages o equal, changed, or majorly changed predictions) for identical prompts across three runs.

Figure 2: LLM evaluation template, as published by Schmidt et al. (2024)

6. Agentic AI as emerging trend

Agentic AI refers to the emerging trend of using artificial intelligence tools to solve complex multi-step problems autonomously, while interacting with code, websites, software tools, or carrying out tasks over a period of time.

One example for this is Anthropic's recent experiment 'Project Vend' where the LLM Claude Sonnet 3.7 was given the task to manage a real vending machine business in the Anthropic office; with access to a starting budget, ability to search for and order stock online, ability to take payments via Venmo, and to receive and act on customer feedback¹⁸.

¹⁸ <https://www.anthropic.com/research/project-vend-1?ref=blog.mozilla.ai> (last accessed 18/07/2025)

This experiment shows that it is possible to apply AI agents to tasks that involve research, analysis, and planning in a real-world scenario, using online resources and human input to shape actions. Karunanayake (2025) describe opportunities for agentic AI in clinical practice to aid diagnostics, decision making, patient support, and documentation (Karunanayake, 2025). An AI agent for evidence synthesis might, theoretically, be able to carry out multi-document extraction and synthesis, if prompted correctly and given appropriate tools. This would, for example, involve steps to search the content of PubMed after creating a search query, download results, perform automated data extraction, and to provide a summary of the results. However, agentic AI is currently only an emerging trend and research evaluating its accuracy and safety for automating evidence synthesis is not yet available.

7. Conclusion

Current research suggests that using LLMs to automate data extraction may increase efficiency in systematic review workflows, but high quality and large-scale head-to-head comparisons against humans in systematic review contexts are lacking. When using LLMs, researchers need to factor in costs of accessing them, environmental impact of training and running them, and most importantly the cost of doing a methodologically sound manual validation initially and whenever the underlying model or the data characteristics change. Direct comparisons of LLMs vs. PLMs are often biased towards one architecture's strengths. More rigorous, comprehensive, and meaningful automated validation methods are needed, especially when applying LLMs to new domains such as toxicology and mapping research where early studies have shown a large potential of time-savings compared to previous manual or semi-automated approaches.

While LLMs hold promise for increasing efficiency in systematic review workflows, this commentary underscores the important need for rigorous, fair, and reproducible evaluation. Head-to-head comparisons with human performance are lacking, and validation methods designed for specific architectures might bias results in favor of one model type over another. It may also be useful to define the accuracy and precision required for certain applications where humans-in-the-loop verification may be necessary for systematic reviews to support regulatory actions for example. Consensus on transparent, best-practice-aligned methods is needed to realise the potential of automation in the future.

There exist multiple stakeholder groups with an interest in automation, each facing different challenges with respect to LLM-use in evidence synthesis:

- Researchers who develop prompts and apply LLMs in downstream projects should familiarise themselves with best practices concerning prompt development processes and dataset splitting, and commit to share their prompts, model version, and if applicable their code as part of their write-up. This familiarisation process can be accelerated by reading scientific literature, taking part in training courses, workshops, or consulting [selected other high-quality online instructional materials such as blog articles and videos](#) ^{19, 20}.
- Tool developers that integrate generative AI should consider not only access and environmental costs, but also the burden of maintaining methodologically sound validation - especially when models or data input characteristics change over time. They should continuously validate their methods, give clear guidance to users, and if applicable share evaluation results in the form of clear, absolute numbers.
- Other stakeholders include [Policy makers and agencies such as the FDA, EMA, and NIH](#) who increasingly explore LLM utility across domains (e.g., in clinical, toxicological, and regulatory science)
- For a more detailed description of stakeholders in evidence synthesis and tailored recommendations, readers may also refer to the drafts of the three documents in the [RAISE guidance](#) (Thomas et al., 2025).

(Thomas et al., 2025) To support responsible LLM research across domains such as toxicology and evidence-based medicine, we advocate for adoption of structured evaluation and reporting practices like the template developed during the 2023 EvidenceSynthesis Hackathon. This template provides useful practical guidance during the steps of protocol development and planning of methods by prompting its users to consider dataset size, splits, research questions, and appropriate validation metrics. During write-up, the template provides a concise and clearly structured way of presenting relevant information. This facilitates not only the write-up process for

¹⁹ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=dSCFk168vmo> and <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=2CIIQ5KZWUM> (last accessed 03/06/2025)

²⁰ <https://medium.com/data-science-at-microsoft/evaluating-llm-systems-metrics-challenges-and-best-practices-664ac25be7e5> and <https://www.techtarget.com/searchenterpriseai/definition/data-splitting> (last accessed 03/06/2025)

[authors, but also reproducibility and analysis of published automation methods, including the issues addressed in this commentary.](#)

8. Conflict of interest and declaration of interest

Financial conflict of interest:

Do you, your family, close relations or acquaintances, currently have, have had in the last 5 years, or expect to have in the next 2 years, any financial interests (potential gains or losses) that could be affected by your submitted publication? None (all authors)

Other conflicts of interest:

None (all authors)

Research interests:

Some authors declare a research interest in the field of automated data extraction in health-related disciplines, including current and previous research projects and memberships of organizations.

International collaboration for the automation of systematic reviews ([ICASR](#)) members: LS, VRW, JT.

Tools: [EppiPPI-Reviewer](#) (JT, LS), Dextr (VRW, AAR, CPS), Sciome SWIFT tools (LS).

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Thomas.

CRedit statement created using Tenzing web-app (Kovacs et al., 2021)²¹.

10. Data availability

Appendix Maps A contains HTML files showing evidence maps with the 17 LLM papers mentioned throughout this commentary. One map shows extracted data (eg. PICO, N participants, ..) vs. study type (eg. RCT, cohort study, ..). The other map shows extracted data vs. text source (eg. abstract, title, full text). These maps can be opened and viewed in any internet browser, for example on Chrome or Firefox.

The appendix files can be accessed from here:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14893133><https://osf.io/bh27x/>

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12. Use of artificial Intelligence in preparing this manuscript

OpenAI's GPT-o3 was used to help with the detection of informal language and to suggest replacements or re-phrasing of selected sentences.

²¹ <https://rollercoaster.shinyapps.io/tenzing/> (last accessed 17/02/2025)

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